

MICROBIOLOGICAL SAFETY AND CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF DEFATTED BLACK SOLDIER FLY LARVAE (BSFL) MEAL

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ABSTRACT

In the past few years, the growing food crisis has increased the demand for alternative foods and feeds with minimal negative environmental impact. To a large extent, insects and their products meet this demand. At the same time, insect farming is gaining more and more popularity as part of the food industry for the production of high-quality feed materials for animals. In the European Union, one of the permitted and most commonly used insect species is the Black Soldier Fly (BSF) (*Hermetia illucens*). The final products obtained from BSF larvae are a source of essential nutrients and successfully replace traditional feeds. Concerning the quality and safety of feed raw materials, in the present study the chemical composition and some microbiological parameters were determined in different batches of BSF insect meal. The results showed that all the tested batches of BSFL meal were excellent protein sources. The presence of *Enterobacteriaceae*, *Salmonella spp.*, and *Clostridium perfringens* was not found in any of the examined samples.

Key words: Black soldier fly (BSF), *Hermetia illucens*, larvae, defatted insect meal, chemical composition, microorganisms.

Introduction

One of the main problems facing modern humanity is the deepening food crisis in connection with a rapidly growing population (Kousar *et al.* 2021). The need to feed the population and food production puts constant pressure on the environment (Flachowsky and Meyer, 2015). Food is the main source of crucial macro and micro nutrients such as protein, carbohydrates, fats, vitamins, and minerals (Diamond A. 2021). Proteins are essential substances, supplying the organism with vital amino acids (Brestensky *et al.* 2018). A fundamental source of protein with high biological value for the human body is products of animal origin like meat, milk, fish, egg, etc. (Young and Pellett 1994; Day *et al.* 2022). According to Ritchie *et al.* (2017), meat product consumption has increased three times in the last five decades, with more than 340 million tons of meat produced worldwide annually. A trend of increasing consumption of animal protein was also documented by Lu *et al.* (2022). Considering that nearly 70% of the costs in animal husbandry are spent on animal feeding as well as the rapid pace of development of this sector, the feed production will have a serious negative impact on the environment (Makkar, 2018). The livestock breeding is estimated to be the source of 15% of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and an important factor in global warming (Capper, 2020; Gomez-Zavaglia *et al.* 2020).

In connection with this, modern society is increasingly focusing on the search for more affordable alternative food sources, with high quality and nutritional composition as environmentally friendly as possible (Madau *et al.* 2020). Products from various insects meet this demand to a large extent, with more and more scientific research proving the advantages of this type of innovative raw materials.

The species Black soldier fly (Hermetia illucens) and its larvae deserve special attention in the production of insect feed raw materials. The excellent nutritional value as well as the larval ability to digest various organic wastes, make BSF one of the most promising insect species as a sustainable source of processed animal protein (PAP) (Abd El-Hack *et al.* 2020). *Hermetia illucens* is also present in the list of insects farmed for the production of feed raw materials approved by the European Union (Commission Regulation (EU) № 893/2017).

The aim of the present study was to determine the chemical composition of DF BSFL meal, as well as the microbiological safety in relation to the presence of some pathogens specified in European legislation.

Materials and methods

Samples of 30 different batches of defatted insect (DF) meal obtained from 12-day-old larvae of BSF, produced by Nasekomo AD, Bulgaria, were analyzed. For all samples it was determined their proximate composition, defined as moisture, crude protein, crude fat, and crude ash. The dry matter content of samples was assessed by oven drying the samples at 105°C until constant weight, and water content was determined as the weight difference before and after oven-drying. For the crude protein, the nitrogen content was determined following the Kjeldahl method and the value was multiplied by a conversion factor of 6,25. Crude fat content was determined by petroleum ether extraction by the Soxhlet method. Crude ash content was determined by incineration of samples at 550°C in a muffle furnace. Three replicate samples were analyzed for each treatment. Results of the study were presented in tables, indicating average values with standard deviation, as well as the maximum and minimum values for the relevant indicator.

The defatted BSFL meal was also tested for the presence of *Salmonella spp.*, *Enterobacteriaceae* and *Clostridium perfringens* according to the following methods:

- ISO 6579-1:2017 – Horizontal method for the detection, enumeration and serotyping of *Salmonella*.
- ISO 21528-2:2017 Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of *Enterobacteriaceae*.
- ISO 15213-2:2024 Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of *Clostridium spp.*

Results and discussion

Hermetia illucens (Linnaeus, 1758) Fig. 1 also known as the Black Soldier Fly (BSF) is a cosmopolitan species of insect belonging to the order *Diptera*, family *Stratiomyidae*, subfamily *Hermetiinae* (Caruso *et al.* 2013; Surendra *et al.* 2016; Cai *et al.* 2022). BSF is a holometabolic insect, undergoing various stages of complete metamorphosis during its developmental period (Peters *et al.* 2014). The life cycle of the insect includes five distinct developmental stages – egg, larva, pre-pupa, pupa and imago (Martinez-Sanchez *et al.* 2011; Caruso *et al.* 2013). The BSF larvae (BSFL) (Fig. 2) and the products they obtain are commonly used to feed pigs, poultry, fish, and pets (Barragan-Fonseca *et al.* 2017).

Figure 1: Black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens*)

Figure 2: Black soldier fly larvae

Chemical composition

The summarized values for the chemical composition of defatted BSFL meal, as well as the maximum and minimum levels for each of the investigated indicators were presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Proximate chemical composition of defatted BSFL meal (% dry basis)

Analysed parameter	Average±SD	Min	Max
Moisture content, %	1.73±0.58	0.95	3.01
Crude protein content, %	56.20±2.70	51.81	60.24
Crude fat content, %	12.36±2.14	8.99	17.75
Crude ash content, %	9.84±1.12	7.82	11.86

In general, the BSFL are used for the production of defatted and full-fat meals (Lu *et al.* 2022). The nutritional composition of the two types of meal can vary considerably (Zulkifli *et al.* 2022; Macwan *et al.* 2023) with the most significant differences in the crude protein and crude fat content (Barragan-Fonseca *et al.* 2017; Lu *et al.* 2022). The defatted meal is obtained after full or partial extraction of fat, and the values of CP are in direct correlation with those of CF. The decrease of fats leads to an increase in protein content (Veldkamp *et al.* 2012; Zozo *et al.* 2022). According to Spranghers *et al.* (2017), the defatted BSFL meal could reach a protein content of over 60%. This circumstance was also confirmed by the available results, as the maximum CP level was 60.24% and the minimum 51.81%, respectively. The average crude protein content of DF BSFL meal was (56.20 ± 2.70 %), which was higher than a conventional soybean meal 48 % (NRC, 2012) and lower than a fish meal (60–72%) (NRC, 1998). The current result agreed with the findings of earlier studies from 2022, where it was 56.11% (Zozo *et al.* 2022) and 56.10 % (Shah *et al.* 2022). The moisture content was the indicator with the lowest value of 1.73±0.58 %, which differed from the obtained results reported by other authors – 6.02 % (Saputra and Lee 2023) and 9.8 % (Attia *et al.* 2023) respectively. The maximum water content in the present study was 3.01% which was in accordance with Chobanova *et al.* (2023) who found a 3.7 % moisture level in BSFL meal. According to Monteiro dos Santos *et al.* (2023) the proximate crude fat content of DF BSFL meal was 10–12 %, which was in line with the data obtained in this study (CF – 12.36±2.14 %). The lipids extraction from these products not only increases the protein content, but also improves its digestibility, and also facilitates storage in relation to lipid oxidation of the feeds (Surendra *et al.* 2016). Crude ash is the inorganic part of the forage and refers to mineral content levels in feed (Rohman *et al.* 2021). BSFL larvae are characterized by a high mineral concentration and crude ash content between 9 and 28 % (Finke, 2013; Makkar *et al.* 2014). Many authors explained it by the high levels of calcium found in the larvae of the insect, as a result of secretion and deposition of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) from

the epidermis of the BSF (Barragan–Fonseca *et al.* 2017; Macwan *et al.* 2023). It was proven that the defatting process has also been shown to increase crude ash levels (Zozo *et al.* 2022; Saputra and Lee 2023). In the current study, the average crude ash content was 9.84 ± 1.12 % and it was in close agreement with the earlier studies where the researchers reported CA – 10.5% (Adeoye *et al.* 2020) and 9.25% (Weththasinghe *et al.* 2021).

The observed variations in the values of the studied indicators might be due to different reasons specifically the processing method (Zulkifli *et al.* 2022), type, quantity and quality of substrate used (Barragan–Fonseca *et al.* 2017), age of larvae (Macwan *et al.* 2023), and abiotic environmental factors during rearing (Lu *et al.* 2022). Despite the differences found in the values of some of the studied parameters with those reported in the literature, it was reaffirmed that the BSFL meal could successfully replace some of the conventional feed materials due to its high nutritional stability.

Microbiological safety

According to Regulation (EU) No 142/2011, protein derived from farmed insects falls under the category of 'processed animal protein' (PAP). The same Act also lays down clear microbiological criteria in relation to the presence of *Salmonella spp.*, *Enterobacteriaceae* and *Clostridium perfringens* in this type of raw materials. Table 2 presents the microbiological results obtained for all 30 batches of DF BSFL meal.

Table 2: Microbial results of defatted BSFL meal (log cfu/g)

Analysed parameter	Defatted BSFL meal* (n=30)
<i>Salmonella spp.</i>	Non detected
<i>Enterobacteriaceae</i>	< 10
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	< 10

* The results for all 30 batches were the same.

The presence of *Salmonella spp.* and *Enterobacteriaceae* in food and feed is a major microbiological indicator of their hygiene (Bessa *et al.* 2021). On the other hand, *Cl. perfringens* are regularly detected pathogens in food and feed (Casagrande *et al.* 2013), and according to Vandeweyer *et al.* (2021), it is also frequently associated with the food safety of various species of edible insects. In the present research both *Enterobacteriaceae* and *Cl. Perfringens* were below the detection limit (10 cfu/g), and *Salmonella spp.* was not detected in 25 g of samples. These results were in full compliance with the European safety standards for Feeds set out in Regulation 142/2009, namely to not detect *Salmonella* in 25 g of product, and *Enterobacteriaceae* and *Cl. Perfringens* in 1 g of product respectively.

It has been found that microbial loads of products derived from insects are largely dependent on the type of substrate used in rearing, as well as the method of larval processing (Bessa *et al.* 2021). Of all the possible killing methods for BSF larvae, blanching and HPP treatments gave the best results in terms of reducing bacterial contamination (Larouche *et al.* 2019; Campbell *et al.* 2020).

Conclusion

In conclusion, DF BSFL meal had excellent nutritional qualities in terms of essential nutrients. Low water content and markedly high crude protein levels were found in all samples tested. The positive correlation described in the literature for the relationship between fat reduction and protein

increase was confirmed. In the analysed batches *Enterobacteriaceae* and *Cl. Perfringens* were below the detection limit (10 cfu/g), and *Salmonella* was not detected in 25 g of samples, which was in line with the microbiological criteria laid down in the EU legislation. Based on the results obtained and the literature review, the great potential of BSFL meal as an alternative substitute to conventional protein feed in animal nutrition was confirmed.

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